

STUDIES ON TORSIONAL STRENGTH OF CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES SHAFT BY INOVATIVE SHEET WINDING

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1. Abstract

In this study for the alternative of conventional steel rod by high strength alloy, we evaluated static strength of carbon fiber composites shaft under torsional loading to fulfill the requirement of weight reduction, acceptable cost and additional performance for automotive or industrial application. To maximize the strength, we developed novel winding method considering the fracture mechanism. As a result of experiment, we found this innovative method significantly improve the static strength around twenty percent compared with conventionally designed shaft having same material usage and stacking composition of lamina angle. In other words, this result makes it possible to reduce carbon fiber consumption around twenty percent. Here after we name this novel method as Simultaneous Multi-Ply Winding. For simplicity, describe as SMPW [1].

2. Background

Under the increasing demand to improve environmental issues, many countries settle individual regulation against earth warming gas emission and make effort to suppress that amount aggressively [2]. Fulfilling these current, zero emission vehicle such as hybrid and/or full electric vehicle has been developed and released by manufactures. However there remain some conflicts like mass increase by complex power system and shorter continuous mileage. Weight reduction of automobile body is one of most effective and common measure to reduce environmental load and it expect to applicable through every kind of vehicle. As most common former case, carbon composites are utilized as primary structure of airplane because of their superior relative strength and rigidity [3]. One most effective candidates being to weight reduction of vehicle is power train axle transferring torque from engine/motor to wheel. Some torque axles by high strength alloy rod are already substituted by hollow composites tube and

drastically reduce weight [4, 5, 6, 7]. Yet from our latest result, it has been confirmed that the strength of these composite shafts only remains from 60 to 70 percent of their own theoretical strength expected from raw materials. The composites torque shafts are commonly fabricated by filament winding method using angle ply laminate, but there are some challenges. The difficulty to secure matrix resin and the limited degree of freedom on stacking sequence, for instance.

Especially, poor strength expression ratio mentioned above directly affects material usage and cost. Although the weight reduction of that industrial application is achieved by carbon composite alternative, we have to fabricate with feasible cost taking into account the steel's price structure. In addition, we have to guarantee consistent quality for mass production from ten thousand to hundred thousand pieces of parts.

Studies on torsional response of cylindrical shaft are very limited. Some of that are mechanical analysis on cross ply or angle ply solely [8], increasing number of ply results more strong by stress redistribution in sole angle ply [9], and study on inter-lamina shear response under torsion-compression combined loading [10]. Thus, studies on torsional response of composite shaft, composed of angle ply together with other ply, is very seldom so far.

In this study, to solve those industrial challenges, we have investigated torsional strength improvement by unique sheet winding method SMPW [1] that wound angle and other plies simultaneously and also tried the fabrication machine development for that innovative manufacturing process [11].

3. Concept to Improve Strength

Under torsional load, cylindrical shaft put pure shear state on their wall. Generally such torque conveying shaft is mainly composed by paired angle ply, and then one side angle ply of 45 degree in laminate shaft will be compressed. Therefore over

the certain load, initial failure will be occurred as some of the following; fiber buckling, inter-lamina separation or fiber splitting. To improve the static strength, we hit 90 degree hoop ply layup together with angle ply simultaneously. As a result, that composites tube has continuous spiral laminate structure. In this structure, the hoop ply will be expected to back angle ply and act as anti-backing reinforcement then suppress the fracture of them.

4. Experiment

4.1. Materials

For the cylindrical composites shaft, we used carbon fiber prepreg composed by “Trayca T700-SC” manufactured by Toray Industries, Inc. for fiber reinforcement and 250degF curable toughened epoxy resin for matrix. This Prepreg material has 125 grams per square meter of areal fiber weight and 67 percent fiber volume fraction.

4.2. Composites Shaft

Each composites shaft by above prepreg was prepared by winding on steel tubular mandrel using originally developed sheet winding machine under precisely controlled pressure and speed. Raw prepreg wound on mandrel were over-lapped by heat shrinkable tape under controlled tension prior to cure. Heat cure was carried out at 130 centigrade with 0.45MPa autoclave pressure in 4 hours. Mandrel diameter is 33.5mm correspond to shaft inner diameter. Test specimens were cut into 320mm length. Stacking number of all specimens kept 18 ply. In this study, axial direction of cylindrical specimen defines as 0 degree of reinforcement direction. As shown in Table 1, Laminate structures were composed by the combination of 90 degree ply as hoop layer and ± 45 degree angle ply as a torsional reinforcement. In SMPW, the set of the angle and the hoop ply where prepreg are cut in three times the length of the circumference was rolled up twice on the mandrel so that have 18-ply spiral structure. In addition, comparing Type 37 and C-G-1, we compare the difference of production method. Both specimens have completely same laminate structure and prepared by our SMPW. In addition, Type 37 is made by more sophisticated winding method to avoid fiber wrinkle [1]. By means of ultrasonic scanning, we have confirmed Type 37 has more uniform structure with fewer defect than C-G-1 by conventional method.

4.3. Torsional Test

As shown in Fig.1, hydraulic torsional fatigue tester by SUM Electro Mechanics Co., Ltd.. was employed to evaluate torsional rigidity and strength.

Code	Laminate Structure	Winding
Type21	$[(+45/-45)_2/90/(+45/-45)/90_2]_2$	Modified SMPW Hoop ply off-set
Type37	$[(+45/-45/90)_3]_2$	Modified SMPW
C-G-1	$[(+45/-45/90)_3]_2$	SMPW
C-S-1	$[(+45/-45)_2/90_2]_3$	Conventional

SMPW: Simultaneous Multi-Ply Winding

Table 1 Laminate structure of carbon fiber composites tube and winding method

Maximum capacity is 5kNm. Torsional load was applied as sine wave. Oscillation amplitude and frequency was ± 45 deg and 0.02Hz respectively. During the experiment, acoustic emission event count is recorded by AE-900M sensor from NF Corporation.

Fig. 1 Photograph of experimental setup of torsional test

5. Result and Discussion

5.1 Torsional Behavior and AE observation

The relationship between torsional angle and moment of two types of laminate are shown in Fig.2. Observed AE signals are also indicated on light vertical axis. With the displacement, torsional moment increase and show non-linear behavior gradually. Between the same stacking number ply specimens, these show almost same rigidity but there were significant difference on failure strengths. AE event count also shows obvious difference. In Table 2, we compare the estimated strength by classical laminate theory and measured actual value with that incidental expression ratio. The relative improved ratio is also indicated with parenthesis derived from C-S-1's strength as 1.0.

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Fig. 2. Relationship between moment, AE event count and torsional angle
a) Type 37, b) C-S-1

Most significant findings are following two issues; The C-G-1's strength made by SMPW is improved several percent than C-S-1 that has common alternating sequential laminate structure composed by angle and hoop ply commonly use for torque shaft. Especially in Type 21 and 37 by improved production method with SMPW to earn more uniform internal structure and lesser fiber wrinkle, those become several percent more strong than C-G-1, if comparison with C-S-1 that become around twenty percent.

Design Code	Torsional Strength / Nm		Exp/CLT
	CLT*	Experiment	
Type21	2043	1981(1.16)	0.97
Type37	2425	2027(1.19)	0.84
C-G-1	2425	1819(1.07)	0.75
C-S-1	2133	1701(1.00)	0.80

* CLT: Classic Laminate Theory

Table 2 Predicted, measured static strength and their expression ratio

5.2 Winding Machine Development

We developed new layup machine adapted to modified winding method SMPW for sustainable mass production process. Composites shafts with small diameter are commonly fabricated using parallel rolling table with handwork. On the other hand, long composites cylinders with large diameter are manufactured by rolling machine equipped three rotary cylinders; one is for pressurized and remaining are for backing up mandrel. Our strategy is that rolling several plies simultaneously. The winding process must be possible to absorb the circumference length difference of each ply and make composites cylinder with lesser void and fiber wrinkle. Therefore these conventional machines are not applicable for this purpose.

Then we developed the novel mechanism by rotating mandrel moving horizontally to wind multiply prepreg which placed on fixed flat base plate [11]. The mandrel is pressurized by cylinder covered with elastic material and this pressure distribution is precisely controlled by high performance pneumatic cylinder. Developed layup machine is shown in Fig.3.

Fig. 3. Photograph of developed winding machine, prototype model for trial production (Pat. pend.)

The existence of internal defects is observed by ultrasonic measurement using 5M Hz probe. Data is not shown here. The strength improvement results by three type composites are shown in Fig.4. From C-S-1 to C-G-1 by handwork SMPW, it is confirmed 10 percent improvement. Additionally more 10 percent improved by sophisticated SMPW procedure with novel machine. In addition, it should be confirmed clearly improved that strength dispersion becomes smaller and quality consistency goes higher.

Fig. 4 The strength improvement results by three type composites
a) Conventional separately wind laminate
b) SMPW
c) Modified SMPW by present original machine

6. Conclusion

In this study, we evaluate several cylindrical composites shafts by carbon laminate in order to ensure maximum strength and reliability with minimum material usage. Improvement of laminate stacking sequence and sheet winding production process result the ultimate strength goes twenty percent higher than conventional concept shaft. In future work, we will try to prove numerically that anti-buckling effect by SMPW's spiral laminate structure. And also we will evaluate the effect on fatigue limit of this technology. This SMPW technology should be confirm greatly contribute to reduce weight, strengthen and save carbon fiber material to meet cost requirement for automotive parts; typically for light-weight torque shaft like propeller or drive axle to achieve ultimate performance. This technology is also applicable wide range of industrial application.

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